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● A check-list of longicorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of Huanglong Nature Reserve, Sichuan, China

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Abstract: The paper listed 18 species of 16 genera belonging to the family Cerambycidae from Huanglong Nature Reserve, Sichuan, China, three of which are new record species from Sichuan, China.

Keywords: longicorn beetles, new records, taxonomy

● 中国四川黄龙保护区天牛名录

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摘要: 本文记录了中国四川黄龙保护区鞘翅目天牛科昆虫 16 属 18 种, 其中 3 种为四川省新纪录种。

关键词: 天牛, 新纪录, 分类学

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Introduction

The Sichuan Huanglong Provincial Nature Reserve is located in Songpan County, Aba Tibetan and Qiang Autonomous Prefecture, Sichuan Province, China. It serves as a critical corridor for the exchange of giant panda populations within the Minshan Mountain Range and has been designated as a Class A priority conservation area.

From July to August 2024, the corresponding author was invited by Professor Fu-Ming Shi (Hebei University, Baoding, China) to participate in an insect resource survey in Huanglong Nature Reserve, Sichuan. During this survey, a total of 18 species belonging to three subfamilies were collected and identified, including three species were reported for the first time in the Sichuan Province, China.

Material and methods

All habitus photographs were taken with a Canon 5D Mark II digital camera equipped with a Canon EF 100mm f/2.8L IS USM lens. All photographs were edited using Adobe Photoshop CC.

The materials examined for this study also referenced the works of Hua *et al.* (2009) and Jiang & Chen (2001). The specimens are deposited in the Insect Collection, College of Agriculture, Yangtze University, Jingzhou, Hubei, China (YZU).

List of species

Family Cerambycidae Latreille, 1802

Subfamily Lepturinae Latreille, 1802

1. *Carilia latiuscula* (Holzschuh, 1993) 阔翅银花天牛

Fig. 1A

Material examined. 1♂, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Munigou, July 21, 2024, coll. by Yun Li.

Distribution. China (Sichuan).

2. *Ischnostrangalis davidi* (Pic, 1934) 大卫纤花天牛

Figs 1B, C

Material examined. 1♂, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Fengping Village, July 26, 2024, coll. by Quan Zhang; 4♂♂3♀♀, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Niuqingshan, July 18, 2024, coll. by Chao-Kun Yang.

Distribution. China (Sichuan).

3. *Lemula pilifera* Holzschuh, 1991 毛圆眼花天牛

Fig. 1D

Material examined. 1♀, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Munigou, July 21, 2024, coll. by Xiao Yang.

Distribution. China (Sichuan, Fujian, Hubei).

4. *Leptura rufoannulata* Pic, 1933 弱带花天牛

Fig. 1E

Material examined. 1♀, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Munigou, July 21, 2024, coll. by Xiao Yang.

Distribution. China (Sichuan, Fujian, Hubei).

FIGURE 1. A *Carilia latiuscula* (Holzschuh, 1993) B, C *Ischnostrangalis davidi* (Pic, 1934) D *Lemula pilifera* Holzschuh, 1991 E *Leptura rufoannulata* Pic, 1933 F *Leptura barkamica* Holzschuh, 1998 G, H *Parastrangalis communis* Holzschuh, 1993 I *Chlorophorus eleodes* (Fairmaire, 1889). Scales = 5mm.

5. *Leptura barkamica* Holzschuh, 1998 巴花天牛

Fig. 1F

Material examined. 1♀, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Munigou (Erdaohai), August 1, 2024, coll. by Li-Kun Zhong; 1♀, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Munigou (Erdaohai), August 7, 2024, coll. by Ping Wang.

Distribution. China (Sichuan, Yunnan, Xizang).

6. *Parastrangalis communis* Holzschuh, 1993 普异花天牛

Figs 1G–H

Material examined. 1♂1♀, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Niuqingshan, July 18, 2024, coll. by Chao-Kun Yang.

Distribution. China (Sichuan).

Subfamily Cerambycinae Latreille, 1802**7. *Chlorophorus eleodes* (Fairmaire, 1889) 榄绿虎天牛**

Figs 1I, 2A

Material examined. 1♂, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Fengping Village, July 26, 2024, coll. by Wen-Bo Yi; 1♀, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Shuanghe Village, August 7, coll. by Ping Wang.

Distribution. China (Sichuan, Hubei, Guizhou, Xizang, Shaanxi, Yunnan, Xinjiang, Jiangxi, Chongqing, Guangxi).

8. *Cleomenes tenuipes tenuipes* Gressitt, 1939 三带纤天牛 new provincial record

Fig. 2B

Material examined. 1♂, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Niuqingshan, July 18, 2024, coll. by Chao-Kun Yang.

Distribution. China (Sichuan, Shaanxi, Hubei, Zhejiang, Guangxi, Yunnan, Taiwan), Vietnam, Laos, India, Malaysia.

9. *Demonax venosulus* Holzschuh, 2006 连纹刺虎天牛

Fig. 2C

Material examined. 1♂, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Fengping Village, July 26, 2024, coll. by Yun Li.

Distribution. China (Sichuan).

10. *Callidium flavosignatum* (Pu, 1991) 黄斑扁胸天牛 new provincial record

Fig. 2D

Material examined. 1♀, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Munigou, July 21, 2024, coll. by Chao-Kun Yang.

Distribution. China (Sichuan, Gansu, Qinhai).

Subfamily Lamiinae Latreille, 1825**11. *Acalolepta permutans permutans* (Pascoe, 1857) 金绒锦天牛**

Fig. 2E

Material examined. 1♂, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Munigou, July 26, 2024, coll. by Chao-Kun Yang.

Distribution. China (Sichuan, Shaanxi, Henan, Hubei, Hunan, Anhui, Jiangxi, Zhejiang, Xizang, Guangdong, Guizhou, Guangxi, Hong Kong, Taiwan), Vietnam, Japan.

FIGURE 2. A *Chlorophorus eleodes* (Fairmaire, 1889) B *Cleomenes tenuipes tenuipes* Gressitt, 1939 C *Demonax venosulus* Holzschuh, 2006 D *Callidium flavosignatum* (Pu, 1991) E *Acalolepta permutans permutans* (Pascoe, 1857) F *Coscinesthes porosa* Bates, 1890 G *Exocentrus spineus* Holzschuh, 2007 H, I *Glenea relicta relicta* Pascoe, 1858. Scales = 5mm.

FIGURE 3. A *Monochamus sparsutus* Fairmaire, 1889 B *Nupserha infantula* (Ganglbauer, 1889) C *Nupserha testaceipes* Pic, 1926 D *Pterolophia zonata* (Bates, 1873). Scales = 5mm.

12. *Coscinesthes porosa* Bates, 1890 豹天牛

Fig. 2F

Material examined. 1♂, China: Sichuan, Songpan, Mofanggou, July 17, 2024, coll. by Chao-Kun Yang.

Distribution. China (Sichuan, Yunnan, Xizang, Zhejiang).

13. *Exocentrus spineus* Holzschuh, 2007 刺勾天牛

Fig. 2G

Material examined. 1♂, China: Sichuan, Songpan, Fengping Village, July 26, 2024, coll. by Wen-Bo Yi.

Distribution. China (Sichuan, Shaanxi, Guizhou).

14. *Glenea relicta relicta* Pascoe, 1858 榆并脊天牛

Figs 2H-I

Material examined. 1♀, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Niuqingshan, July 18, 2024, coll. by Chao-Kun Yang; 1♂, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Shuanghe Village, August 7, 2024, coll. by Ping Wang.

Distribution. China (Sichuan, Hubei, Jiangxi, Zhejiang, Jiangsu, Anhui, Shaanxi, Guizhou, Hunan, Fujian, Guangxi, Hainan, Guangdong), Vietnam, India, South Korea.

15. *Monochamus sparsutus* Fairmaire, 1889 麻斑墨天牛

Fig. 3A

Material examined. 1♂, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Fengping Village, July 26, 2024, coll. by Wen-Bo Yi.

Distribution. China (Sichuan, Anhui, Fujian, Henan, Hubei, Hunan, Jiangxi, Shaanxi, Taiwan, Yunnan, Zhejiang).

16. *Nupserha infantula* (Ganglbauer, 1889) 黑翅脊筒天牛

Fig. 3B

Material examined. 5♂♂5♀♀, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Shuanghe Village, August 7, coll. by Ping Wang.

Distribution. China (Sichuan, Hubei, Shaanxi, Yunnan, Gansu, Guizhou, Hebei, Hunan, Zhejiang, Guangxi, Fujian, Jiangxi, Guangdong).

17. *Nupserha testaceipes* Pic, 1926 黄腹脊筒天牛

Fig. 3C

Material examined. 1♂, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Niuqingshan, July 24, 2024, coll. by Yun Li.

Distribution. China (Sichuan, Hubei, Guizhou, Heilongjiang, Jilin, Guangxi, Hainan, Shandong, Guangdong, Gansu, Fujian, Hunan, Jiangsu, Jiangxi, Zhejiang, Anhui).

18. *Pterolophia zonata* (Bates, 1873) 黄带坡天牛 new provincial record

Fig. 3D

Material examined. 1♂, **China: Sichuan**, Songpan, Fengping Village, July 26, 2024, coll. by Quan Zhang.

Distribution. China (Sichuan, Taiwan), North Korea, South Korea, Japan.

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Additional information

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